

DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN MODERN SECONDARY SCHOOL MANAGEMENT

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Abstract. *In the given scientific and theoretical approaches related to human capital and its management, the issues of their implementation, which are considered as an urgent problem of the current period, are the main criterion for establishing a continuous pedagogical process in the management of educational institutions and monitoring the quality of education. This process requires organizing the management system of an educational institution in a qualitatively new format of electronic education, that is, transferring management to a digital state. The article also reflects on changes in new paradigms of education in the context of the development of a digital educational environment, issues of digitalization technologies in modern management, for example, in blended education.*

Keywords: *information, equipment, line, cellular communications, e-mail, multimedia, information and communication technologies, management, process.*

It is important to suggest that in the formation period of a new generation, it is necessary to update educational conditions and technologies aimed at developing the active, creative personality of the teaching staff. Instilling moral values in the younger generation is the main task of the education system and the entire state. The formation of a personality capable of making decisions adapted to constantly changing conditions and new reality requires the implementation of the results achieved in the field of management of the educational system and achievements in the field of modern pedagogical technologies.

The issue of using digitalization technologies in modern management of secondary schools and its importance, the interaction of law and digitalization have been studied by many researchers. For example, in the scientific works of F. Iskhakova, F. Khamdamova, S. Sadikov, M. Akhmedshaeva, O. Khusanbaev, the legal aspects of the use of information and communication technologies in the activities of government bodies were studied [3, 5, 1]. Particularly, the legal regulation of information and communication technologies in Uzbekistan, the formation and development of legal documents on electronic government, the main stages and features of the legal regulation of the provision of interactive public services were studied by L. Iskhakova [3], the formation and development of the legal basis for the e-government system, the legal basis for the use of modern information and communication technologies in the activities of public authorities and management within the framework of the e-government system were studied by S. Sadikov [5].

The management process depends on human capital, and as an integral feature of various types of its activities, one can note the professional knowledge, practical skills and level of preparation for scientific analysis of the manager. The importance of procedural, ethical, motivational, goal-oriented, professionally-oriented components of training managers for professional activities is emphasized, for example, skills in modeling various phenomena of management processes. At the same time, he develops his own responsibilities, the ability to predict activities and his position in relation to its digitalization. Thus, the manager will be directed

to modeling education as an aspect of the employee's methodological capital. Human capital management refers to the practices, processes and systems used to manage and develop an organization's employees.

In management, the human component is, on the one hand, the heaviest part of all assets, and on the other hand, people are the only element capable of producing value in a product. The productivity of an organization's human capital is not always predictable and is under the control of the employer. The practice of human capital management is based on the belief that the workforce, like other assets such as land, buildings and equipment, is part of a company's capital. Successful human capital management usually begins with the process of finding and hiring a workforce.

Sh. Akramova emphasizes that the formation of an innovative economy requires the development of a new concept of personnel training, and it should be based on the following principles:

- formation, development and self-determination of a creative personality create conditions for its manifestation;
- focus on training highly qualified and highly intelligent specialists.

Thus, human capital and its management means a person's ability to effectively use acquired knowledge, that is the ability to practically demonstrate his scientific potential.

It is known that the management of educational institutions and its digitalization are considered as modern approaches, and the introduction of digitalization technologies into the educational process and the modern management system of secondary schools indicates a general trend covering the field of education. Increased interest in informatization of the education system is associated with global processes encompassing modern society, that is, the formation of the digital generation, digital person and therefore creates the need to introduce information and communication technologies into the education system and the management of educational institutions.

The development of the education system in modern conditions through digitalization in the modern management of secondary schools makes new demands on the construction of the educational process, including the creation of a modern electronic information and educational environment using advanced educational technologies, the implementation of an education management strategy and the adaptation of educational materials taking into account individual features. With the rapid adoption of e-learning and the development of digital learning environments, educational formats are changing, and the educational paradigm is shifting to a hybrid learning process that combines offline and online learning.

Certainly, digitalization technologies are based on the use of multimedia and Internet technologies to improve the quality and opportunities of education, and the use of an innovative approach to education. Many foreign open and virtual educational institutions operate on the principle of e-education, which competes with traditional forms of education.

According to I.Yu. Pashenko, digitalization is used in a narrow and broad sense. In a narrow sense, digitalization is the process of changing information, that is, giving it digital form. In a broad sense, digitalization is a process that improves the quality of life through the modernization of various spheres of human activity, including the management of various social processes [4].

Despite the large theoretical and practical material collected in the modern practice of managing a comprehensive school, the processes associated with managing a comprehensive educational institution cause difficulties [2].

According to a group of authors, lines such as cellular communications, e-mail, cellular and satellite technologies, wireless and cable communications, multimedia, and the Internet represent a wide range of digital technologies [6]. Based on the above definition, it can be noted that information and communication technologies are used in all spheres of human activity, and the use of digital technologies in the management of educational institutions is no exception. In addition, it is possible to optimize the decision-making process in the management of an educational organization only with the help of modern digital technologies.

It should be noted that managing a general education institution requires a set of actions aimed at establishing an orderly, continuous pedagogical process and organizing the transfer of the educational institution management system to a qualitatively new format, that is, to a digital format. When we talk about a set of actions, we understand the set of actions of both the heads of the educational organization and the school teachers. This process is best implemented using a management model based on the fundamental principles of the formation of management activities [2].

Definitely, the introduction of digitalization technologies into the modern management of secondary schools opens up broad prospects from the management of an educational institution to the management of the educational process. Having information, processing it and delivering it to the addressee, in particular, participants in the educational process, allows you to effectively manage and, as a result, receive and apply qualitatively new pedagogical technologies. According to a number of authors, the use of information technologies in the management of the educational process helps to improve the quality and culture of management activities and ensure flexible work in conditions of dynamic development [2].

Analyzing methodological approaches to the problem of using digitalization technologies in modern management of secondary schools, it is advisable to develop a trajectory for optimizing the process of managing an educational institution. The authors were able to theoretically and experimentally confirm the feasibility of introducing a management model using information and communication technologies in educational institutions.

By summarizing it should be suggested that the use of digitalization technologies in the modern management of secondary schools is becoming relevant in order to overcome the problems and difficulties that arise simultaneously with the development of digital technologies and new digitalization trends that lead to the spread of electronic education.

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